

**EVALUATING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION
PROGRAM IN SELECTED PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS
IN TAYTAY RIZAL**

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Evaluating the Implementation of a Physical Education Program in Selected Public Secondary Schools in Taytay Rizal

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Abstract

The study assessed the implementation of a Physical Education Program in Selected Public Secondary Schools in Taytay Province of Rizal. Data was collected from administrators, teachers, and students using descriptive surveys and comparative research design. The respondents deemed the curriculum, with Philosophy and Objectives being the most important. However, facilities and equipment were poor. There was no significant difference in philosophy and objectives, organization and administration, curriculum and instruction, and measurement and evaluation. However, a significant difference was found in facilities and equipment, indicating the need for improvement. The study recommends higher authorities to address these issues, providing teacher and administration in-service education to improve students' attitudes and knowledge towards Physical Education. Improvements in sports facilities and equipment utilization will enhance students' performance in competitions. The program should allocate maintenance funds and other expenditures and reach local governmental officials for construction or improvement. Further studies with other variables are suggested to enhance the effectiveness and proper implementation of the Physical Education program.

Keywords: *effectiveness, inclusive education, implementations, Physical education Program, and student's performance in Physical Education*

Introduction

Physical education (PE) occupies a critical position within the broader educational framework, contributing significantly to the holistic development of students. As articulated in "The Youth of Today," the collective responsibility of educators, sports leaders, parents, and government officials is to equip the youth with the necessary skills and resilience to navigate the challenges of the future. The vitality and advancement of a nation hinge on the presence of fit, vibrant, intelligent, and morally sound citizens. Consequently, one of the paramount objectives of education is to cultivate young individuals into well-rounded and ethically grounded citizens who are poised to lead the nation forward.

In alignment with this educational mandate, the Philippine Constitution, specifically Republic Act Article XIV, Section 19, underscores the State's commitment to promoting physical education and encouraging sports initiatives, league competitions, and amateur sports. This legal framework aims to foster self-discipline, teamwork, and excellence while nurturing a healthy and alert citizenry. Further reinforcing this commitment, President Proclamation No. 406, issued in the mid-1990s, designated the decade from 1990 to 2000 as the Decade of Physical Fitness and Sports in the Philippines. This proclamation highlights the intrinsic value of physical education in enhancing attributes in children that are not adequately developed through other academic subjects. The ramifications of neglecting physical education are profound; equipping individuals for diverse professional roles without fostering their physical strength, health, and resilience severely constrains their potential.

This research endeavors to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the challenges and opportunities associated with the implementation of the PE program in selected public schools within the Taytay Rizal district. It aims to explore how PE programs in the Philippines can be optimized by examining the perspectives of teachers, administrators, and students. The findings of this study will serve as a valuable resource for educators, curriculum designers, and other stakeholders interested in adopting best practices for the effective implementation of physical education pedagogical programs tailored to the needs of Filipino students.

The backdrop of this study reveals that secondary school PE programs in the Taytay Rizal district are beset by numerous challenges. A significant issue is the lack of resources necessary to support effective PE programs. A study conducted in the Taytay Rizal District (2019) indicates that many schools lack essential infrastructures such as gyms, sports fields, and play areas, which severely limits the range of activities that can be conducted during PE classes. Additionally, the scarcity of sports equipment—ranging from balls and cones to mats—further constrains the variety of physical activities available to students. This deficiency in resources adversely impacts both instructional quality and the overall learning experience for students.

Moreover, the Taytay Rizal district faces a shortage of adequately trained PE teachers. According to a study by the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017), numerous schools in the region employ teachers who are not specialized in physical education but are nonetheless tasked with teaching it as part of their workload. It is imperative that PE instructors possess the requisite knowledge, skills, and resources to effectively deliver PE programs and positively influence students' learning outcomes.

Another critical factor is the lack of collaboration among education stakeholders and community authorities within the Taytay Rizal

district. Research indicates that there is a notable absence of partnerships with local sports clubs and fitness centers, which could enhance the resources, skills, and experiences available to students (Taytay Rizal District, 2019). This lack of effective collaboration has limited the diversity of activities offered in PE classes, thereby restricting opportunities for students' physical, social, and emotional development.

Considering these challenges, this paper proposes strategies to enhance engagement in PE programs in high schools within the Taytay Rizal district. Three primary approaches are suggested to ensure quality resource allocation for PE programs: first, the establishment of adequate infrastructural facilities and the provision of necessary equipment; second, the implementation of professional development opportunities for PE teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills; and third, the formation of partnerships with regional sports clubs, fitness centers, and similar organizations to broaden the resources and expertise available for PE programs. By addressing these challenges and capitalizing on available opportunities, this study aims to improve the quality of PE instruction, foster students' physical, social, and emotional development, and promote lifelong physical activity and healthy habits within the Taytay Rizal district.

Research Questions

The primary objective of this study was to conduct to evaluate the Implementation of a Physical Education Program in Selected Public Secondary Schools in Taytay Rizal. Specifically, the study aimed to address the following research questions:

1. What is the status of the implementation of the Physical Education Program in secondary schools concerning different components?
 - 1.1. philosophy and objectives;
 - 1.2. organization and administration;
 - 1.3. curriculum and instruction;
 - 1.4. facilities and equipment; and
 - 1.5. measurement and evaluation?
2. To what extent is the Physical Education Program implemented, as perceived by administrators, teachers, and students, regarding the following aspects:
 - 2.1. facilities;
 - 2.2. equipment;
 - 2.3. monitoring and evaluation; and
 - 2.4. administrative support?
3. Are there significant differences in the extent of implementation of the Physical Education Program, as perceived by the three groups of respondents, in relation to the aspects mentioned above?

Literature Review

The implementation of physical education (PE) programs in secondary schools remains an important area of study especially for the wellbeing and fitness of the students. However, the inclusion of disabled children in the programs remains a challenge, and this has prompted a number of studies to advocate for adaptive physical education (PE) where the needs of diverse students are specifically addressed. For example, Subroto et al. (2021) asserts that it is the responsibility of education systems to use adaptive physical education as a strategy for assisting young people with disabilities to achieve their maxim potential and for aiding their personal growth and social development (Subroto et al., 2021). And, when working with students with disabilities and utilizing movement games to break the activity monotony, the benefits are two-pronged as PE programs have a positive impact on both physical fitness and metabolic health (Dimyati et al., 2022). Moreover, Goh et al. (2020) assert that optimal practices including teacher education and administrative support have a significant impact on the effectiveness of such interventions in schools. A majority of participants, both preservice and in-service teachers, identified administrative support and collaboration as key elements for the success of CSPAP (Goh et al. 2020). This furthers the research by Haynes-Maslow et al.

As pointed out by Haynes-Maslow et al. (2019), limited resources and infrastructure are obstacles to effective delivery of PE programs but having strong partnerships can enhance the implementation process. There is a need for parents to be involved in the program and also physical activities integrated in other subjects in order to promote PE as well (Goh et al., 2020). The processes of design and evaluation of the curriculum are also vital to the performance of the PE programs. Xu et al. (2014) argue that having a good curriculum design which both targets relevant education goals enhances expected results in the teaching of physical education (Xu et al., 2014).

There have been suggestions for new ways of doing things that include the use of movement games and sensory training to improve the students' motor skills and physical performance (Li, 2023; Dao, 2021). The need for these practices is provided by studies that show physically active school children engage in practices that are beneficial to health such as improved cardiorespiratory fitness as well as numerous studies which prove schools as an institutional buffer to obesity (Lucas et al., 2019; Cocca et al., 2020). In addition, the authors highlight the need for PE instructors to participate in professionally oriented courses and seminars in order to hone their skills, as mares and members such as Escrivá-Boulley et al. (2018) found that professional development that is need-supportive has the tendency to be positively correlated with the motivational style of the teachers and thus, physical activity of the students (Escrivá-Boulley et al., 2018). This is significantly pertinent in the context of the Philippines where there are institutions of learning that have

embraced the idea of adopting PE programs but do so amidst difficulties that are associated with resources and level of teacher readiness to implement training programs (Tolentino et al., 2022). Teachers require adequate training and support mechanisms that are designed to assist them in delivering PE programs that are appropriate for students with diverse needs.

To conclude, the effective integration of physical education programs in secondary schools, specifically in Taytay Rizal, is dependent on the efficiency of the adaptive programming offered, the commitment from the administration, the design of the curriculum, and the continuous training of the teachers. Furthermore, innovative practices and the involvement of the community could improve the health status of the students.

Methodology

This research utilized the descriptive survey method and Descriptive-Comparative Research design. A descriptive survey method was used to evaluate the implementation of a physical education program in public secondary schools in Taytay Province of Rizal. In choosing an appropriate sample size, Slovin's formula was utilized, while a stratified random sampling technique was used to depict the population adequately. A descriptive-comparative research design is ideal for answering the question about differences in the perceived implementation of the Physical Education program. This design involves describing how each of the three groups (e.g., students, teachers, administrators) perceives different aspects of the program (e.g., curriculum, facilities, teacher training) and then comparing those perceptions statistically. This allows you to determine if significant differences exist in how each group views the program's implementation. You would achieve this by developing a survey to gather data from each group, analyzing the results using statistical tests, and drawing conclusions about the extent of implementation based on the findings.

The research design according to the study was based on descriptive surveys and descriptive comparative enabled the researcher to give a detailed analysis of the physical education programs performances. Pre-testing of the questionnaires was conducted with physical education teachers from Casimiro A. Ynares Sr. Memorial National High School, Muzon National High School, Central Taytay National High School and Manuel I. Santos Memorial National High School to test the designed data collection instruments on respondents for clarity and efficacy. The respondents to this study were teachers, who were actively involved in the teaching of physical education, the school management and a sample of the students drawn randomly from the specified secondary schools within the Taytay, Province of Rizal. This group composition was broad enough to comprehend all angles on the implementation of the physical education program.

The information was obtained by administering specific questionnaires as well as conducting interviews with the participants. The questionnaires were grouped into four parts and were further focused on the following aspects: schools and respondents' biographical data were obtained in the first part of the questionnaire, the second part analyzed in-service education of teacher-respondent, the third part sought professional images of the respondents, the fourth on the other hand examined the physical education program itself. Questionnaires were also given out but for more response rate and reliability of the results, they were individually completed by the researcher while informal interviews were held to collect additional information and clarify the responses given to the questionnaire. After collecting data, the responses were sorted out according to the study's objectives and were further presented and analyzed with statistical tools such as the F test which was used to assess degree of agreement among the respondents towards specific aspects of the physical education program.

The ethical issues were given high priority at all stages of the research. Prior to the data collection, all participants were made to sign consent forms so that they were properly informed of the nature of the study and the scope of their rights. All the participants were guaranteed that the study was voluntary and that one had the choice of withdrawing at any point during the study without any consequences. They ensured that the anonymity of the participants and the information they provided was adhered to and that all information was de-identified. Also, the research was conducted according to the ethical principles of educational institutions and research organizations so as to uphold dignity and respect of all subjects in assessing the physical education program.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Composite table on the Status of Implementation of the Physical Education Program in Secondary Schools*

Criteria	Principal		Teacher		Student		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Philosophy and objectives	3.47	A	4.30	SA	4.14	A	4.18	A
Organization and administration	4.53	SA	4.10	A	4.07	A	4.12	A
Facilities and equipment	4.07	A	3.42	A	3.96	A	3.85	A
Curriculum and instruction	4.42	SA	3.89	A	4.07	A	4.06	A
Measurement and evaluation	4.67	SA	4.09	A	4.09	A	4.11	A
Overall	4.23	SA	3.96	A	4.07	A	4.06	A

Table 1 shows the Composite table on the Status of Implementation of the Physical Education Program in Secondary Schools in terms of different components.

As reflected in Table 1, as perceived by the administrator respondents, on the status of implementation of Physical Education Program in Secondary Schools, obtained the highest overall mean of 4.23 verbally interpreted as “Strongly Agree”. For Teachers’ respondents obtained the lowest overall mean of 3.96 verbally interpreted “Agree”. On the other hand, as for the students’ respondents obtained the overall mean of 4.07 verbally interpreted as “Agree”. The finding implies that the administrator respondents perceived the aspect of Philosophy and Objectives, Organization and Administration, Facilities and Equipment, Curriculum and Instruction and Measurement and Evaluation as “Agree”. This means that the school administrators are aware of how to manage the school and eventually improve the learning capacities of the students through Philosophies and Objectives of the program.

Moreover, with respect to an aspect on the “Philosophy and Objectives” obtained the highest overall mean of 4.18 interpreted verbally as “Agree” and “Facilities and Equipment” obtained the lowest overall mean of 3.85 interpreted verbally as “Agree”. This means that much attention should be given to meet the needs of the Facilities and Equipment. The findings of the present study support the study of Gravador (2006) as cited by Penaranda (2012) stated that, inadequacy of available P.E. apparatuses and equipment facilities and supplies affect the implementation of the P.E. Program. Since the School administrators got the highest in rank, this means that they were very much aware of their responsibilities underlying on the policies and programs implemented in the school. This also shows that they were competent managers to effect improvement in the performance of their institution.

With respect to students’ respondents, obtaining the second highest top the rank is likewise contributed to the development and improvement of the programs, activities, and gave their assistance and collaborative effort to the institutions. Hence, they were the clientele that would be given valuable support to the educational process; therefore, the school should cater them with proper knowledge, skills and abilities and adept with healthy attitudes towards learning.

Furthermore, for the teachers who are very much in need to provide them institutional trainings and educational seminars to upgrade their involvement in educative process is highly recognized and it is also necessary that the school should always look into the welfare of every teacher. With respect to Status of Implementation of the Physical Education Program, it can be gleaned that teachers and students interpreted as “Agree” while the administrators interpreted “Strongly Agree”. This means that the schools give priority to this aspect; hence, this will contribute for the improvement of the program as well as the school.

Problem # 2

Table 2. *Computed mean on the Extent of Implementation of the PE Program as perceived by the Administrators, Teachers and Students with respect to Facilities*

Facilities	Principal		Teacher		Student		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
1. Athletic field	3.67	HS	1.87	Sub	2.13	Sub	2.10	Sub
2. Badminton court	3.00	St	2.13	Sub	1.87	Sub	1.86	Sub
3. Baseball court	3.00	St	1.17	N	1.45	N	1.44	N
4. Basketball court	3.00	St	1.70	N	1.53	N	1.58	N
5. Chess room	3.33	St	2.43	Sub	1.84	Sub	2.03	Sub
6. Dressing room	3.00	St	2.65	St	2.20	Sub	2.22	Sub
7. Drinking facilities	3.67	HS	2.55	Sub	2.79	St	2.77	St
8. First aid clinic	2.33	Sub	3.19	St	3.27	St	3.26	St
9. Football field	2.33	Sub	1.00	N	1.36	N	1.33	N
10. Gym	3.00	St	1.05	N	1.54	N	1.50	N
11. Hand washing facilities	3.00	St	2.86	St	3.11	St	3.08	St
12. Lawn tennis court	3.00	St	1.27	N	1.50	N	1.49	N
13. Lecture room	3.67	HS	3.14	St	3.44	HS	3.39	St
14. Music room	2.33	Sub	1.50	N	2.42	Sub	2.25	Sub
15. Sepaktakraw court	3.33	St	1.64	N	1.87	Sub	1.86	Sub
16. Shower room	2.33	Sub	1.18	N	1.34	N	1.31	N
17. Softball diamond	2.33	Sub	1.00	N	1.27	N	1.23	N
18. Swimming pool	1.00	N	1.00	N	1.10	N	1.07	N
19. Table tennis court	2.33	Sub	1.41	N	1.60	N	1.58	N
Average	2.83	St	1.85	Sub	1.98	Sub	1.96	Sub

The table above shows the computed weighted mean on the extent of implementation of the P.E. program as perceived by the administrators, teachers and students with respect to facilities.

As revealed by the respondents, the principal has an average of 2.83 which is verbally interpreted as Standard; while the teachers and students noticed that the facilities are Substandard as shown by the computed average of 1.85 and 1.95. The overall computed mean of 1.96 reflects the perception of the respondents about the facilities as Substandard.

The researcher supports the study of (FAROOQ & AHMED, 2021) as he disclosed that facilities were regarded as motivating factors in making both students and teacher work effectively and efficiently.

Table 3. *Computed mean on the Extent of Implementation of the PE Program as perceived by the Administrators, Teachers and Students with respect to Equipment*

Equipment in Specific Sports	Principal		Teacher		Student		Overall	
	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI	Mean	VI
Athletic (Average)	1.73	N	2.16	Sub	2.19	Sub	2.21	Sub
Arnis (Average)	1.27	N	2.51	Sub	2.00	Sub	2.21	Sub
Basketball (Average)	3.67	HS	2.89	St	2.71	St	2.82	St
Badminton (Average)	4.00	HS	2.60	St	2.68	St	2.73	St
Throwing Events (Average)	1.58	N	2.64	St	2.09	Sub	2.30	Sub
Baseball/ Softball (Average)	3.59	HS	2.32	Sub	2.05	Sub	2.18	Sub
Chess (Average)	2.33	Sub	3.19	St	2.63	St	2.76	St
Gymnastics (Average)	1.45	N	1.31	N	1.60	N	1.55	N
Lawn Tennis (Average)	2.53	Sub	1.35	N	1.97	Sub	1.86	Sub
Sepak Takraw (Average)	3.13	St	1.94	Sub	2.52	Sub	2.46	Sub
Soccer (Average)	1.00	N	1.60	N	1.68	N	1.69	N
Swimming (Average)	1.00	N	1.04	N	1.41	N	1.33	N
Table Tennis (Average)	3.67	HS	2.67	St	2.78	St	2.83	St
Taekwondo (Average)	1.00	N	1.84	Sub	1.96	Sub	2.02	Sub
Volleyball (Average)	1.93	Sub	2.61	St	2.29	Sub	2.38	Sub

In table 3 reveals those significant disparities in the perceived adequacy of equipment across various sports as reported by principals, teachers, and students. The data indicates that the overall mean scores for equipment in specific sports range from "None" (N) to "Standard" (ST), highlighting a concerning trend in the availability and quality of resources necessary for effective physical education.

For instance, the mean score for athletic equipment is notably low, with principals rating it at 1.73 (N), while teachers and students rated it at 2.16 (Sub) and 2.19 (Sub), respectively. This suggests a consensus among all groups that the equipment is inadequate for facilitating a robust athletic program. Similarly, in sports such as Arnis and Gymnastics, the ratings remain in the "None" category, indicating a critical lack of resources that could hinder the development of students' physical skills and overall engagement in physical activities.

Conversely, sports like Basketball and Badminton received higher ratings, with Basketball averaging a mean score of 3.67 High Standard from principals and 2.89 (ST) from teachers, suggesting that these sports are better supported in terms of equipment. This disparity raises questions about the allocation of resources and the prioritization of certain sports over others within the PE curriculum. The findings are consistent with previous research indicating that inadequate facilities and equipment significantly impact the performance and motivation of physical education teachers, which in turn affects student engagement and outcomes (Panganiban, 2019).

Furthermore, the data reveals that sports such as Soccer and Swimming received the lowest ratings, both at 1.00 (N) across all groups, indicating a complete absence of necessary equipment. This lack of resources is particularly alarming given the recognized importance of diverse physical activities in promoting health and fitness among adolescents. The absence of equipment not only limits students' opportunities for participation but also undermines the overall objectives of the PE program, which aims to foster a lifelong appreciation for physical activity.

The evaluation of the PE program in Taytay, Rizal, underscores a critical need for improved resource allocation and support for physical education. The disparities in equipment availability across different sports highlight the necessity for a comprehensive review of the PE curriculum and its implementation, ensuring that all students have access to quality physical education experiences that promote their physical, social, and emotional well-being.

Table 4 presents the Computed mean on the Extent of Implementation of the PE program as perceived by the Administrators, Teachers and Students respect to Controlling.

The data given represents the results of a quantitative evaluation or survey conducted to assess the performance of individuals involved in a sports-related setting, potentially within a school or educational institution. The data includes mean ratings for various aspects of control, principle, teacher, and student performance, along with an overall average score.

Analyzing the mean ratings, it is evident that the respondents generally indicated positive perceptions of the evaluated aspects. The overall average ratings for control, principal, teacher, and student performance were above the midpoint of the Likert scale, indicating a favorable perception overall. Specifically, the highest mean ratings were observed in areas such as evaluating performance according to sports plans, keeping coaches, training staff, and athletes well-informed, and encouraging athletes to maintain academic excellence alongside sports. These areas received mean ratings ranging from 4.33 to 4.67, indicating a strong agreement or positive perception.

On the other hand, aspects such as efficient management of financial and material resources and checking if training plans are being accomplished based on targets and quality standards received slightly lower mean ratings, ranging from 3.50 to 3.65. While still indicating agreement, these areas may benefit from further attention and improvement.

Table 4. *Computed mean on the Extent of Implementation of the PE program as perceived by the Administrators, Teachers and Students with respect to Monitoring and Evaluation*

		<i>Monitoring and Evaluation</i>							
		<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Keep coaches, training staffs and athlete well informed.	4.33	SA	4.30	SA	3.73	A	3.89	A
2.	Appraises performance and take corrective actions.	4.00	A	4.17	A	3.53	A	3.71	A
3.	Evaluates performance according to sports plan.	4.67	SA	4.00	A	3.63	A	3.77	A
4.	Determines the scope of the job and divides them for efficiency and effectiveness.	4.33	SA	3.91	A	3.55	A	3.66	A
5.	Keeps quality training instruction through effective supervision?	4.67	SA	4.17	A	3.62	A	3.78	A
6.	Performs efficient management of financial and material resources.	3.50	A	3.62	A	3.56	A	3.59	A
7.	Checks if training plans are being accomplished based on targets and meet quality standards.	4.33	SA	3.65	A	3.54	A	3.59	A
8.	Keeps record and counseling services of erring athletes.	4.67	SA	3.83	A	3.53	A	3.62	A
9.	Encourages athletes to maintain academic excellence on top of sports.	4.33	SA	4.35	SA	3.59	A	3.80	A
10.	Orients academic teachers to give consideration and make up classes of athletes.	4.33	SA	4.26	SA	3.58	A	3.78	A
<i>Average</i>		4.37	SA	4.03	A	3.58	A	3.72	A

The data suggests that the individuals involved in the sports-related setting demonstrated positive perceptions of the evaluated aspects. The findings can serve as a basis for further discussions and actions to enhance the performance and effectiveness of the control, principal, teacher, and student roles within the context of the sports program. It is important to consider these quantitative results alongside qualitative feedback and additional data to gain a comprehensive understanding of the strengths and areas for improvement within the evaluated setting. The findings conform to the premise of Alberto (2016) stated that control is the process that measures current performance and guides it toward some predetermined goal. This checks the existing actions against some desired results.

Table 5. *Computed mean on the Extent of Implementation of the PE program as perceived by the Administrators, Teachers and Students with respect to Administrative Support*

		<i>Administrative Support</i>							
		<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Student</i>		<i>Overall</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Organizes intercampus athletic meet to discover potential athletes.	4.00	A	4.26	SA	3.78	A	3.90	A
2.	Purchases top of the line equipment and provide standard facilities.	3.67	A	3.52	A	3.57	A	3.57	A
3.	Conducts seminars in sports faculty, coaching and training.	3.67	A	4.00	A	3.58	A	3.63	A
4.	Finds sports funds by solicitation, scholarship from alumni and friends of the said school	3.00	MA	4.00	A	3.62	A	3.71	A
5.	Forms and train competitive team.	3.33	MA	4.48	SA	3.66	A	3.82	A
6.	Permits varsity teams to participate in an organized friendly competition.	3.67	A	4.39	SA	3.70	A	3.84	A
7.	Finds time to supervise, training instruction and check how it is delivered.	3.67	A	4.39	SA	3.66	A	3.82	A
8.	Provides seminars to the coaches and training staff regarding first aid and sports psychology.	4.00	A	3.96	A	3.61	A	3.67	A
9.	Sends coaches to international and national seminars / conferences.	3.67	A	3.57	A	3.42	A	3.42	A
10.	Involves involved sports personnel in the budget preparation.	4.00	A	3.70	A	3.57	A	3.61	A
11.	Gives incentives for every medal/ award won.	3.67	A	3.87	A	3.91	A	3.95	A
<i>Average</i>		3.67	A	4.01	A	3.64	A	3.72	A

Table 5 presents Computed mean on the Extent of Implementation of the PE program as perceived by the Administrators, Teachers and Students with respect to Administration. Regarding administration, it can be gleaned from table that the principal respondents "Agree" as perceived by that the extent of implementation of P.E. program in almost all given aspects. Moreover, items like 1. "Organizes intercampus athletic meet to discover potential athletes", 8. "Provides seminar to the coaches and training staff regarding first aid and sports psychology" and 10. "Involves concerned sports personnel in the budget preparation." Obtained the highest computed weighted mean of 4.00 all belongs to the verbal interpretation of "Agree".

However, two items obtained "Moderately Agree" these item no. 4. "Finds sports fund by solicitation, scholarship from alumni and friends of the said school" obtained the lowest weighted mean of 3.00 and item no. 5. "Forms and train competitive team" obtained weighted mean of 3.33. As for the teachers' respondents, highest item is no. 5. "Forms and train competitive team" obtained the highest computed weighted mean of 4.48 and the verbally interpreted as "Strongly Agree". Item no. 2. "Purchases top of the line equipment and provide standard facilities" obtained the lowest computed mean of 3.52 verbally interpreted as "Agree".

As perceived by the students on the Extent of Implementation of the PE program Administration in all given aspects are all "Agree".

Item no. 11. “Gives incentives for every medal/ award won” obtained the highest mean of 3.91 interpreted as “Agree” and the lowest item is 9. “Sends coaches to international and national seminars / conferences” with only 3.42 computed mean. The result of the present study confirms the findings of (ADA, 2018) that the effectiveness of the P.E. Program relies on the administrators who affect a forceful type of leadership in an organization.

Problem # 3

Table 6. *Significant difference on the Extent of Implementation of the PE Program as perceived by the three groups of respondents*

		SS	df	MS	F	Sig.	HO	VI
Facilities	Between Groups	2.509	2	1.254	3.612	.029	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	54.876	158	.347				
	Total	57.385	160					
Equipment Athletics	Between Groups	.604	2	.302	.591	.555	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	80.256	157	.511				
	Total	80.860	159					
Arnis	Between Groups	6.821	2	3.411	3.595	.030	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	147.991	156	.949				
	Total	154.813	158					
Basketball	Between Groups	3.120	2	1.560	2.051	.132	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	120.136	158	.760				
	Total	123.256	160					
Badminton	Between Groups	5.342	2	2.671	2.095	.126	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	200.133	157	1.275				
	Total	205.475	159					
Throwing events	Between Groups	7.061	2	3.530	3.229	.042	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	171.658	157	1.093				
	Total	178.719	159					
Baseball/softball	Between Groups	8.109	2	4.054	5.604	.004	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	114.308	158	.723				
	Total	122.417	160					
Chess	Between Groups	6.147	2	3.074	2.469	.088	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	191.732	154	1.245				
	Total	197.879	156					
Gymnastics	Between Groups	1.674	2	.837	1.522	.222	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	85.814	156	.550				
	Total	87.488	158					
Lawn tennis	Between Groups	8.650	2	4.325	5.721	.004	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	117.947	156	.756				
	Total	126.597	158					
Sepaktakraw	Between Groups	8.009	2	4.004	4.512	.012	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	135.797	153	.888				
	Total	143.806	155					
Soccer	Between Groups	1.418	2	.709	.800	.451	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	139.151	157	.886				
	Total	140.569	159					
Swimming	Between Groups	3.071	2	1.535	3.537	.031	Reject	Significant
	Within Groups	67.709	156	.434				
	Total	70.779	158					
Table tennis	Between Groups	2.659	2	1.330	1.155	.318	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	179.634	156	1.151				
	Total	182.293	158					
Taekwondo	Between Groups	2.929	2	1.464	1.633	.199	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	139.932	156	.897				
	Total	142.860	158					
Volleyball	Between Groups	2.497	2	1.248	1.633	.199	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	119.995	157	.764				
	Total	122.492	159					
Controlling	Between Groups	5.353	2	2.676	2.866	.060	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	144.742	155	.934				
	Total	150.094	157					
Administration	Between Groups	2.667	2	1.334	1.562	.213	Accept	Not Significant
	Within Groups	130.673	153	.854				
	Total	133.340	155					

The table above presents the significant difference on the extent of implementation of the P.E. program as perceived by the three groups of respondents.

It was statistically found out that there is no significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents in terms of the equipment with respect to athletics, basketball, badminton, chess, gymnastics, soccer, table tennis, taekwondo, and volleyball since the obtained probability values are 0.555, 0.132, 0.126, 0.088, 0.222, 0.451, 0.318, 0.199 and 0.199 respectively which exceed the 0.05 level of significance. It was shown as well that the obtained probability value of the controlling and administration were 0.60 and 0.213 consequently which exceed the 0.05 level of significance, thus reveals no significant difference on the respondents' perceptions. On the other hand, it was revealed that there is significant difference on the perceptions of the respondents when it comes to the facilities, arnis, throwing events, baseball/softball, lawn tennis, Sepaktakraw and swimming since the computed values were 0.029, 0.030, 0.042, 0.004, 0.004, 0.12, 0.031 correspondingly which were less than the 0.05 level of significance.

The Findings of the study are related to Bandola, et.al (2014). He found out that the area of improvement needing priority attendance covered physical education facilities, equipment and evaluation of P.E. Program.

Conclusions

The study recommends assessing the implementation of the Physical Education (PE) program in Selected Public Secondary Schools, in Taytay Rizal. Observable, as perceived by administrators, teachers, and students. However, it is apparent that there is a deficit of facilities and equipment which if possessed would improve the effectiveness of the program. Equally essential information trends imply that there were no marked differences regarding the implementation of the PE program across selected secondary schools. In addition, various administrators, teachers, and students stressed the demand for improvement of the program in different directions. Regarding the above conclusions some recommendations are suggested. Firstly, higher authorities must undertake accurate World Studies on the intensification of the PE's identified problems as well as the conditions of the PE program. In service training, seminars, sports clinics, and workshops for teachers and administrators should be organized to improve their practice and perception on the subject. In addition, the acquisition of required materials and upgrading of sports facilities must be undertaken to assist students' participation in various sporting activities. It is also advocated that there should be a budget allocation for maintenance and other PE programs related expenditures. Another area that is worth pursuing is working with the local government authorities in the construction of courts or gymnasiums meant for physical education.

The proposed courses of action should focus upon the executive and distinct enhancing of the previous course of action, spanning across the new PE study. Even as this research shows Education is beneficial, also more effort has been realized in the PE Program in Secondary Schools. We aim to support these areas of improvement by offering specifically focused recommendations for the PE program to achieve greater effectiveness and quality of service. PE Program in Secondary Schools can be further developed and promoted only in close interaction and collaboration with other educational establishments and local governing bodies.

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